

Supporting Information:

**Significantly Improved Detection of Molecular
Oxygen by Two-Color Resonance-Enhanced
Multiphoton Ionization**

Itai S. Kallos,^{†,‡} Ilana Bar,[†] and Joshua H. Baraban^{*,‡}

[†]*Department of Physics, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Beer-Sheva 8410501, Israel*

[‡]*Department of Chemistry, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Beer-Sheva 8410501,
Israel*

E-mail: jbaraban@bgu.ac.il

Citations in the SI refer to the bibliography of the main article.

Figure S1: Two-color ($2 + 1'$) resonance-enhanced multiphoton ionization spectra of the $3d$ Rydberg complex of molecular oxygen. The black trace is the ionization signal of jet-cooled O_2 at ~ 5 K ionized by ~ 760 nm after tunable two-photon ultraviolet excitation. The green trace is a mass-gated signal of atomic oxygen showing only two features at the $3d\pi^3\Sigma_1^+$ ($v' = 1$) states.¹⁸ The inset shows an enlarged portion of the mass-gated O signal.

Figure S2: One-color (2 + 1) resonance-enhanced multiphoton ionization spectra of the $C\ 3s\sigma\ ^3\Pi_g \leftarrow X\ ^3\Sigma_g^- (v' = 2)$ F₂ (left) and F₃ (right) transitions at various laser powers. The calculated stick spectrum is taken from Wiederkehr et al.² The experimental spectrum is only partially rotationally resolved at low laser power and unresolved at higher power where the signal is much stronger. The baselines are not shifted, displaying the increase in non-resonant signal. The inset shows the plateau in signal for pulse energies above ~ 20 mJ.